

ЎЗБЕКИСТОН РЕСПУБЛИКАСИ
ОЛИЙ ТАЪЛИМ, ФАН ВА ИННОВАЦИЯЛАР ВАЗИРЛИГИ
ТОШКЕНТ МОЛИЯ ИНСТИТУТИ

“ТУРИЗМ СОҲАСИГА САЙЁҲЛАРНИ ЖАЛБ ҚИЛИШДА МИЛЛИЙ
ҲУНАРМАНДЧИЛИК МАҲСУЛОТЛАРИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ
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“PROSPECTS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF NATIONAL CRAFT PRODUCTS IN
ATTRACTING TOURISTS”

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25 МАРТ 2023 ЙИЛ
ТОШКЕНТ
“TOTISOD-MOLIYA” 2023

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Тақризчилар: Академик С.С.Гулямов
и.ф.д., проф. Т.Т.Жўраев

и.ф.д., проф. Т.З.Тешабаевнинг умумий раҳбарлиги остида

Таҳрир ҳайъати аъзолари: проф. С.Мехмонов, доц. А.Исламкулов, доц. Ш. Синдаров
проф. А.Пардаев, доц. Ғ.Сафаров, проф. Ф.Назарова, доц. Ш.Аллаяровва “Менежмент
ва маркетинг” кафедрасининг барча профессор-ўқитувчилари.

Ушбу илмий маъруза тезислари тўпламида ижтимоий-иқтисодий барқарорликни таъминлашда туризм соҳасига сайёҳларни жалб қилишда миллий ҳунармандчилик маҳсулотларини ривожлантириш истиқболлари бўйича аниқ ечимлар, шунингдек мамлакатимиз ҳамда хорижий йирик иқтисодчи олимлар, тажрибали амалиётчилар, олий ўқув юртларининг профессор-ўқитувчилари, илмий тадқиқот институтлари ва марказларининг етакчи илмий ходимлари, докторант ва мустақил изланувчиларнинг илмий тадқиқот иши натижалари мужассамлашган.

Ушбу нашрда келтирилган барча маълумотлар ва фикр-мулоҳазалар муаллифларга тегишли бўлиб, таҳрир ҳайъати аъзоларининг фикрига мос келмаслиги мумкин. Нашрда келтирилган рақамлар, статистик маълумотлар, фикр-мулоҳазалар учун муаллифлар масъул ҳисобланади.

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КИРИШ СЎЗИ

Янги Ўзбекистонни барпо қилишда олиб борилаётган кенг кўламли ислохотлар самараси ўлароқ бугун мамлақатимизнинг барча жабҳаларида эришилаётган ютуқларни Бутун жаҳон ҳамжамияти эътироф этаётганлиги барчамизни қувонтирмоқда. Бу борада мамлақатимизни ҳар томонлама тараққий эттириш, унинг жаҳон миқёсидаги шон-шуҳратини оширишга катта ҳисса қўшаётган, ёш авлодни соғлом ва баркамол инсонлар этиб вояга етказиш, уларни ватанпарварлик, миллий ва умуминсоний қадриятларга ҳурмат руҳида тарбиялаш борасида Тошкент молия институтида ҳам самарали ишлар амалга оширилмоқда.

Албатта, бугунги ташкил этилган илмий-амалий анжуманни ҳам мазкур ишларнинг давоми сифатида эътироф этишимиз мумкин.

Янги Ўзбекистоннинг Тараққиёт Стратегиясида Туризм соҳасини ривожлантириш масаласи алоҳида мақсад сифатида белгилаб олинган бўлиб, туризмни ривожлантириш бўйича туб бурилиш қилинди ва бу борада кўплаб ислохотлар амалга оширилмоқда. Ушбу **“ТУРИЗМ СОҲАСИГА САЙЁҲЛАРНИ ЖАЛБ ҚИЛИШДА МИЛЛИЙ ҲУНАРМАНДЧИЛИК МАҲСУЛОТЛАРИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ИСТИҚБОЛЛАРИ”** мавзудаги халқаро миқёсидаги илмий-амалий анжуман ҳам ана шу мақсадлар самараси ўлароқ ташкил этилмоқда.

Ушбу Конференцияга ҳамкорлик қилаётган нуфузли хорижий Олий Таълим Муассасалари Австралиянинг Кертин университети, Менежментни ривожлантириш Ҳиндистон Маркази, Г.В.Плеханов номидаги Россия Иқтисодиёт Университети ҳамда Европа амалий илм ва менежмент институтларига шунингдек, Ўзбекистон Республикаси Туризм ва маданий мерос вазирлиги ҳамда Ўзбекистон Ҳунармандлар уюшмасига ўз миннатдорчилигимизни билдирамыз!

Гувоҳи бўлиб турганингиздек, сўнгги йилларда Янги Ўзбекистон туризмни ривожлантириш, бу борада илм-фан ва илмий фаолиятни ҳар томонлама қўллаб-қувватлаш ва натижадорлигини ошириш бўйича аниқ мақсадга йўналтирилган чора-тадбирлар амалга оширилмоқда.

Мамлакат тараққиётининг замонавий босқичида туризм соҳасини ислоҳ этишда амалга оширилаётган кенг кўламли ислоҳотлар илм-фан ва инновация соҳасида ҳунармандчилик соҳасини ривожлантириш ва миллий ҳунармандчилик маҳсулотлари орқали туризм жозибадорлигини ошириш муҳим аҳамият касб этмоқда.

Туризм соҳасига сайёҳларни жалб қилишда миллий ҳунармандчилик маҳсулотларини ривожлантириш илмий фаолиятига оид давлат дастурларини шакллантириш ҳамда мамлакат ҳудудларда миллий бренд маҳсулотларини жаҳон миқёсига олиб чиқиш долзарб масала ҳисобланади.

Ушбу анжуман ишига муваффақият тилаган ҳолда, иштирок этаётган Ҳурматли Меҳмонларимиз ва маърузачиларимизга ҳамда тадбир иштирокчилари ва ташкилотчиларига яна бир бор ўз миннатдорчилигимни билдириб қоламан!

Тошкент молия институти ректори

И.ф.д., профессор Т.З.Тешабоев

МУНДАРИЖА

		бет
№	Кириш	
1	<i>T. Teshabayev.</i> WAYS TO FORM AND DEVELOP TOURISM INFRASTRUCTURE IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN.....	3
2	<i>Peng Xinge.</i> THE IMPACT OF POLICIES ON THE TOTAL FACTOR PRODUCTIVITY OF THE TECHNOLOGY SERVICE INDUSTRY.....	8
3	Д.Х. Асланова.МЕТОДИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ИДЕНТИФИКАЦИИ ТУРИСТСКИХ КЛАСТЕРОВ: НА ПРИМЕРЕ САМАРКАНДСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ.....	16
4	<i>Алимардонова З.М.</i> ҲУНАРМАНДЧИЛИК МАҲСУЛОТЛАРИНИ ДИВЕРСИФИКАЦИЯ КИЛИШ ВА ТУРИЗМ МАКСАДИДА КЕНГ ФОЙДАЛАНИШ ИМКОНИЯТЛАРИ.....	29
5	<i>Маткаримов Ж. Ш.</i> ИЧКИ ТУРИЗМНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШНИНГ ИЛФОР ХОРИЖИЙ ТАЖРИБАСИ ВА УНИ ЎЗБЕКИСТОНДА ҚўЛЛАШНИНГ ИҚТИСОДИЙ АФЗАЛЛИКЛАРИ.....	33
6	<i>Nazarova.F.X Ibragimov Sh,.</i> MILLIY HUNARMANDCHILIKNI RIVOJLANTIRISH SAMADORLIGINI OSHIRISHDAGI.....	43
7	<i>Sh.Allayarov.</i> PROSPECTS OF NATIONAL CRAFT PRODUCTS IN ATTRACTING TOURIST TO THE FIELD OF TOURISM	47
8	<i>B.Sadibekova.</i> MARKETING TADQIQOTINI AMALGA OSHIRISHDA TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING.....	50
9	<i>S.Normurodov , M.Xayrullayeva.</i> TURIZM SOHASI RIVOJLANISHINI BOSHQARISHNING TASHKIL IQTISODIY MEKANIZMI.....	54
10	<i>B.Rahmatullayev.</i> XIZMAT KO'RSATISH SOHASINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA MILLIY HUNARMANDCHILIK TURIZMNI AHAMIYATI.....	59
11	<i>M.Ergashev.</i> TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA CHET EL TAJRIBASIDAN FOYDALANISH USULLARI.....	64
12	<i>S.Boyjigitov, B.Boyjigitiv.</i> MILLIY HUNARMANDCHILIK	67

99	<i>Ҳабибуллаев И, Жумаев А,</i> ТУРИСТЛАР ОҚИМИНИ ЭКОНОМЕТРИК МОДЕЛЛАШТИРИШ ВА ПРОГНОЗЛАШ	384
100	<i>Р.С.Урунов</i> ТУРИЗМ СОҲАСИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ ВА РИВОЖЛАНИШ КЎРСАТКИЧЛАРИНИ МОДЕЛЛАШТИРИШ	390
101	<i>П.Александровна Хамдамова Г.А.</i> СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ И УПРАВЛЕНИЯ В ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ. ...	395
102	<i>Хомидов Қ.</i> ҲУДУДЛАРДА ТУРИСТИК МАЖМУАЛАР ФАОЛИЯТИНИ ШАКИЛЛАНТИРИШ ВА БОШҚАРИШНИНГ ЗАМОНАВИЙ ЁНДАШУВЛАРИ.....	398
103	<i>Холиқов.С</i> THE ECONOMIC IMPORTANCE OF RURAL WOMENS' NATIONAL CRAFTWORK IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN.....	402
104	<i>Холматов.О,Зиядуллаева.Д</i> SHAHRISABZ SHAHRIDA SAYYOHNLARNI JALB QILISH HUNARMANLARNING EKSPORT SALOHİYATINI OSHIRISH.....	406
105	<i>Sh.Allayarov,Alijonov S</i> O‘ZBEKISTONDA TURIZM SOHASIDA RAQAMLI IQTISODIYOT RIVOJLANISHINING MUHIMLIGI.....	410
106	<i>Sh.Allayarov,Erkinjonov.D</i> O‘ZBEKISTONDA TURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH VA UNING ISTIQBOLLARI.....	414
107	<i>F.T.Bazarova,S.S.Esanbekov</i> TURIZM SOHASIDA MILLIY HUNARMANDCHILIK MAHSULOTLARINI SOTUVINI TASHKIL ETISHDA RAQAMLI MARKETINGNING.....	417
108	<i>Ф.Т.Базарова.</i> МАМЛАКАТИМИЗДА ТУРИЗМ СОҲАСИНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШГА ТАЪСИР ЭТУВЧИ ОМИЛЛАР	419
109	<i>Ф.Т.Базарова.</i> ГЛОБАЛ РАҚОБАТ ШАРОИТИДА ТЎҚИМАЧИЛИК КОРХОНАЛАРИ МАРКЕТИНГ ФАОЛИЯТИДА БОЗОРНИ ТАДҚИҚ ЭТИШНИНГ	422
110	<i>Ф.Т.Базарова.</i> КОМПАНИЯЛАР ФАОЛИЯТИДА РАҚАМЛИ МАРКЕТИНГНИНГ АМАЛИЙ АҲАМИЯТИ.....	426
111	<i>Н.О.Рахматуллаева.</i> БАРҚАРОР, АҚЛИИ ВА ГАСТРОНОМИК ТУРИЗМ.....	429
112	<i>Азимова Л.С.</i> ТУРИЗМНИ РИВОЖЛАНТИРИШ АМАЛИЁТИ ВА АМАЛДАГИ ТАМОЙИЛЛАР	430
113	<i>Назарова Ф.Ҳ.Тўйчиева Н.Ф.</i> ҲУНАРМАНДЧИЛИК	432

занжири билан бирлаштирилган туризм бозори субъектларининг маҳаллийлаштирилган гуруҳи бўлиб, уларнинг ўзаро таъсири рақобатбардош кооперативдир.

Туристлик мажмуалар фаолиятини бошқаришда туристик мажмуалар таркибий қисимларига ёндашувларнинг мавжуд иқтисодий ва ташкилий салоҳиятни ҳисобга олган ҳолда бошқарувни ташкил этиш соҳа ривожланишининг ҳозирги босқичида катта аҳамиятга эга. Бу туристик маҳсулотлар ишлаб чиқаришни жадаллаштириш, янги туристик маҳсулотлар ва ҳисматлар турини яратиш, туристик мажмуалар корхоналари ўртасида горизонтал иқтисодий алоқалар даражасини кенгайтириш, туризмда иқтисодий оқимларнинг интенсивлигини ошириш ва соҳа фаолияти билан боғлиқ тармоқларнинг зарурий даражадаги интеграцияси билан боғлиқдир.

Туристлик мажмуалар фаолиятини шакллантириш ва ривожлантириш жараёнида вужудга келадиган бошқарув муносабатлари ҳудудларнинг табиий ва иқтисодий тизимларни яратишда муҳим аҳамият касб этади.

Хулоса ўрнида, туристик мажмуалар фаолиятида оқилона бошқарувни шакллантириш тадбиркорлик тузилмалари, давлат бошқарув органлари ва табиатнинг ўзаро алоқасига асосланади, бу эса вертикал ва горизонтал бошқарув тизимларининг ўзаро бирикишига имкон беради. Вертикал ва горизонтал бошқарув тизимларининг ўзаро бирикиши ижтимоий-иқтисодий рискларни минималлаштиришнинг реал имкониятларини юзага келтиради.

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THE ECONOMIC IMPORTANCE OF RURAL WOMENS' NATIONAL CRAFTWORK IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN

Xoliqov Sulaymon O'tkir o'g'li - PhD student of Tashkent state agrarian university

Abstract: The development of handicrafts and the types of national handicrafts of Uzbekistan are current issues in today's world. A variety of measures are being

implemented in the regions in order to employ people in the country and thus reduce or eliminate poverty. After all, increasing employment is our primary goal right now. It was common until the advent of large-scale industrial production; some industries were even preserved later. It continues to play an important role in some countries' national economies.

Keywords: handicrafts, different types of handicrafts, vitrage (stained glass), our ultimate goal, pandemic.

Craftsmanship, handicraft - a national-traditional small-scale industry based on individual and manual labor using simple tools; the general term for the professions that produce such products.

Pottery and textile production, the first important branches of handicrafts in the Neolithic period, appeared on Uzbekistan's territory. The Great Silk Road played an important role in the trade of handicrafts beginning in the 2nd century BC. Products from the East were valued in European markets during the Middle Ages (steel in the Arab Caliphate, silk, porcelain, and paper in Central Asia and India).

Until the 1920s, all types of handicrafts were practiced in Central Asia. Crafts were important in the production relationships of Bukhara, Samarkand, Kokand, Khiva, and Tashkent (in the 60s of the XIX century 27 types of handicrafts were developed in Khiva, there were 556 shops of craftsmen in the city markets, 2528 farms were engaged in handicrafts in the 1980).

In Uzbekistan, craftsmanship is highly specialized and brings together a range of specialists. There were weavers, satin weavers, carpet weavers, shawl weavers, and felt weavers in the textile industry. Metalworkers included blacksmiths, blacksmiths, coppersmiths, plumbers, and jewelers. For instance, there were leather processing, shoemakers, saddlers, telpaks, postmen, and belt makers. The excellent craftsmen of ancient Karakol are particularly well known. The district currently offers bread baking in a tandoor, wood carving, fine embroidery, goldsmithing, and blacksmithing.

The following areas of handicraft activities are taken into consideration in accordance with the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 216 of 29.07.2009 on measures for the development and expansion of family business and handicraft activities without the formation of a legal entity.

Glassware is processed in the following ways: stained glass, spreading, and glass blowing. Plaster carving, pottery, painting, tin, spools, leather, porcelain, artistic and functional leather, painted miniatures, paintings, ornaments, and embellishments made of enamels are all examples of hand-carved items. Wooden architecture, wood folk crafts, the creation of folk crafts from wood, wood carving, furniture decoration, automated furniture production, carpentry, the creation of musical instruments, and the creation of folk toys are all categories of wood processing.

Compared to other nations, ours places a greater emphasis on the growth of handicrafts because, in some areas, there aren't any industrial companies that employ many people. The rate of unemployment is declining thanks to the growth of handicrafts. The state has established a number of advantages in an effort to promote family businesses and crafts in all regions.

The problem of ensuring the population's economic stability is at the core of these opportunities. Our ultimate objective is to eradicate or significantly reduce poverty in our nation through employment. These expansive activities continue throughout the pandemic.

The President, in particular, had traveled to every region and created a variety of possibilities to boost employment and avoid economic harm. A particular focus was focused on the growth of family businesses and crafts on its basis during a visit to the Fergana region on June 5 of this year. We don't give people fish, but rather educate them how to catch fish and allow them to get it when they need it, as Shavkat Miromonovich put it. The growth of handicrafts and employment with a limited percentage of non-refundable payments were prioritized, depending on the sort of labor accessible to the populace.

The President stopped by the Margilan Handicraft Center while there. Mothers and women, who are the center of every family, are my top priorities, she declared. I'm pleased to see the hope and trust in your eyes. The Lord provides us power, peace, and calm in our nation in proportion to how well we treat women. The pandemic presents a significant challenge to everyone in the world. Nobody had any faith that we could start these businesses under these circumstances. In Fergana, the swallow, transformation is now starting. If God wills, our outcomes will be much better, stated Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

Satin, adras, silk, velvet, and bekasam materials are used to cover the lower floor of the two-story center. A podium, a workshop, and a display of finished goods are located on the first floor. All of the items manufactured here are made totally by hand from pure silk. By paving the path for the growth of such crafts, the population's sources of income are being increased.

The subject of sustaining a steady index of commercial activity through the growth of handicrafts is given particular emphasis in our nation today. The Business Activity Index for May has been made public by the Center for Economic Research and Reform. Following a historic fall in April, quarantine restrictions were slightly increased in May according to the Business Activity Index. This suggests that the economy's business activity has started to rebound.

The Center for Economic Research and Reform's Business Activity Index (IFI) for May 2020 showed increases of 5.6% compared to April 2022 (1056 units), 7.0% compared to May 2021 (930 units), and 39.0% compared to January 2020 (1390 units).

Quarantine limitations increased slightly in May of this year after experiencing a historic reduction in April, according to the Business Activity Index. This suggests that the economy's business activity has started to rebound. When compared to the base period and the same month last year, the IFI is still in a recession.

The component level underwent adjustments. The following components changed in May 2021, causing the business activity index to increase considerably by 5.6% from the previous month and reach 1,056 units: Bank account activity for commercial entities climbed by 7.6%, operating entity activity increased by 0.5%, raw material purchases at the commodities exchange slowed by 3.0%, and brand activity increased by 2.3 times.

The Bukhara region has the highest rate among the regions. The opportunities offered to the craft sectors have led to this outcome. The countrywide index of business activity in May 2020 improved over the previous month in all regions. Substantial growth was seen in the Navoi (24.1%) and Tashkent city (22.8%) regions, as well as Bukhara (43.8%), Surkhandarya (40.1%), Samarkand (35.3%), Jizzakh (32.0%), Andijan (29.2%), and Kashkadarya (24.2%).

In conclusion, it can be mentioned that the growth of Uzbekistan's national handicrafts and their variety are current issues. The growth of handicrafts in the current pandemic will serve as a practical foundation for the growth of tourism in the future by creating employment.

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**SHAHNISABZ SHAHRIDA SAYYOHLARNI JALB QILISH
HUNARMANDLARNING EKSPORT SALOHIYATINI OSHIRISH**

Xolmatov Oybek Ilhomovich

O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasi
Madaniyat va san’atni rivojlantrish jamg‘armasi

Madaniy meros agentligi

boshqarma boshlig‘i o‘rinbosari

XolmatovOybek@umail.uz . tel +998912237676

Ziyadullayeva Dilshoda Anvar qizi

Mustaqil tadqiqotchi

XolmatovOybek@umail.uz . tel +998912237676